

OXIDATION OF HYDROCARBONS IN THE VAPOUR PHASE. PART I. AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS.

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In this laboratory, toluene was oxidised in the vapour phase in the presence of certain vanadium and nickel catalysts when satisfactory yields of benzoic acid and benzaldehyde were obtained (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 11, 185). This work has now been extended further to aromatic hydrocarbons with condensed rings such as naphthalene and phenanthrene. The oxidation was carried out in an electrically heated glass tube with primary and secondary air as described in the above paper. The products of combustion were collected in successive water-cooled receivers which were further cooled with ice in the case of highly volatile products.

The following catalysts were used and their preparation is described below :—

(i) Vanadium pentoxide, prepared by heating ammonium metavanadate, the oxide being fused and obtained in granular form by crushing and sieving.

(ii) Tin vanadate, obtained by slowly adding a dilute solution of stannic chloride to a solution of sodium metavanadate with constant mechanical stirring. A small quantity of asbestos emulsion was added to the vanadium solution when an asbestos support was desired.

(iii) Manganese vanadate was prepared in a similar manner, manganese chloride being used in place of stannic chloride. Pumice was often used as a support and was incorporated in the same way as asbestos.

(iv) Mixed tin and vanadium oxides were obtained by fusing a mixture of the oxides in molecular proportion and crushing and sieving the mass thus obtained.

(v) Mixed nickel and aluminium oxides were obtained by impregnating a mixture of saw dust and aluminium oxide with a solution of nickel nitrate and the mass was carbonised at 800° in hydrogen atmosphere. The product was maintained at a dull red heat in air until all the carbon was burnt off.

The activity of the above catalysts with special reference to the yield of phthalic anhydride from naphthalene and phenanthrene was studied. Variations in the yield of phthalic anhydride were often noticed though the catalyst used and the conditions of the different experiments were not

varied. This was overcome by avoiding any disturbance of the catalyst bed between successive experiments conducted with the same catalyst.

Oxidation of Naphthalene.—Unlike toluene, naphthalene did not yield any aldehyde on oxidation, the main products being phthalic and maleic anhydrides accompanied by small amounts of 1:4-naphthaquinone and traces of benzoic acid and naphthol while carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide were the gaseous products. Phthalic and maleic anhydrides were separated by washing with cold water and were estimated by titration.

The first series of experiments were conducted with a view to determine the optimum quantity of air and the rate of its flow. It was found that excess of air favoured the yield of phthalic acid. As large quantities of heat were evolved in the reaction, the excess of air served to diffuse the heat and prevented abnormal rise of temperature. Variations in the proportion of primary and secondary air did not greatly influence the yield so long as the total volume of air was in sufficient excess. Using the same catalyst, the quantity and proportion of primary and secondary air and the rate of its flow, temperature of the catalyst bed and of the carburettor, the size of the catalyst particles and the catalyst space were varied. Of the different catalysts, mixed oxides of tin and vanadium (in molecular proportion) and tin vanadate supported asbestos were found to have the greatest activity. Thus a yield of 61.2% phthalic anhydride (calculated on the amount of naphthalene used) was obtained with mixed oxides of tin and vanadium (unsupported) as catalyst under the following conditions:

Diameter of catalyst tube (glass),	... 1.5 cm.
Catalyst space	... 6.3 cc.
Air ratio	... 3 times of the theoretical.
Time of contact	... 0.32 sec.
Carburettor temperature	... 172°
Temp. of catalyst bed	... 290°
Naphthalene attacked	... 59%
Yield of phthalic anhydride	... 90%.

As lower furnace temperatures, the product became yellow on account of a higher yield of naphthaquinone while with a longer time of contact (5 sec.) and at the same temperature a higher yield of maleic acid (8.2%) was obtained. With a shorter time of contact, the yield of phthalic anhydride was better but a large amount of naphthalene escaped unoxidised. Thus under the conditions noted above, only 59% of the naphthalene used was attacked and hence the actual yield of phthalic anhydride obtained was 90% of the theoretical yield. When tin vanadate (unsupported) was used as the catalyst, the maximum yield of phthalic anhydride obtained was 51.2%

calculated on the naphthalene used but when the same catalyst was mounted on asbestos, the yield increased to 60%.

Using manganese vanadate supported on pumice as the catalyst and varying the different conditions, a maximum yield of only 30% of phthalic anhydride and 12% of maleic anhydride could be obtained. Apparently manganese vanadate is more drastic in its action and oxidises phthalic anhydride further to maleic anhydride and carbon dioxide.

It may be observed that the catalysts, mixed oxide of tin and vanadium and tin vanadate-asbestos, were used in 15-20 consecutive runs without any appreciable loss of efficiency. The best yields were obtained in the 3rd to the 10th run.

Oxidation of Phenanthrene.—The principal product phthalic anhydride, obtained in the catalytic oxidation of phenanthrene, was contaminated with traces of maleic anhydride, naphthalic anhydride, quinone and phenanthrol. Unlike liquid phase oxidation which attacks the middle ring and gives diphenic acid, it is the side ring which is susceptible to gaseous phase oxidation. 1:4-Phenanthraquinone was identified by colour reactions, *i.e.*, (i) with concentrated sulphuric acid green colour was obtained and (ii) with Lanbaheimer colour test which consists in treating acetic acid solution of the quinone with toluene containing thiotoluene. With sulphuric acid bluish green colour is obtained, when shaken with ether, red-violet colour is obtained.

The carburettor temperature was maintained at a higher level and the arm of the carburettor and the exposed portion of the reaction tube were heated by means of nichrom wire to about 350° to prevent any deposition of phenanthrene. Using the tin vanadate-asbestos as the catalyst, a maximum yield of 22.35% phthalic anhydride was obtained under the following conditions.

Diam. of the reaction tube, 1.5 cm.

Time of contact, 0.35 sec.

Catalyst space, 12.5 cc.

Carburettor temp., 190°.

Air ratio, 3½ times of the theoretical.

Catalyst temp. 420°.

Lower temperatures and shorter time of contact favoured the formation of quinones which turned the product yellow. At higher temperatures, colourless products free from quinones were obtained. As in the case of naphthalene, a large excess of air was necessary to diffuse the heat of the reaction and prevent abnormal rise of temperature. On account of a large number of rings to be opened up, the yield of phthalic anhydride is naturally

less than in the case of naphthalene and a large amount of the hydrocarbon is completely burnt off to carbon dioxide. By careful fractional crystallisation of the oxidation products, a beautiful orthorhombic crystalline substance was obtained which from its acid character, m.p. 175° and molecular weight 195.2 (cryoscopic method) was identified as naphthalic anhydride. It was evidently formed by the opening up of the side ring of phenanthrene nucleus.

Mechanism of Oxidation.—The formation of the various intermediate products, *i.e.*, traces of naphthol, 1:4-naphthaquinone, phthalic anhydride, benzoic acid and maleic anhydride and carbon dioxide formed in the oxidation of naphthalene may be explained by the following scheme of reactions with the help of the hydroxylation theory of Bore :

It may be observed that only *p*-quinone (1:4) was identified and no other quinone could be detected. It is, therefore, assumed that at high temperatures, hydrogen atoms in *para* position are preferentially hydroxylated.

Before the rupture of the naphthalene nucleus took place only naphthaquinone and minute traces of naphthol were the products that could be detected, the dihydroxy naphthols were extremely susceptible to oxidation and hence their presence could not be detected. No benzene or benzoquinone were found which seems to indicate that phthalic anhydride

is directly oxidised to maleic anhydride by the rupture of the benzene nucleus followed by partial decarboxylation and that the oxidation does not proceed through benzene and benzoquinone.

In the case of phenanthrene the course of the oxidation may be represented by the following scheme :—

Before the rupture of the phenanthrene nucleus takes place, phenanthraquinone is obtained by the oxidation of the side ring. This assumption is justified by the fact that no diphenic acid could be detected while naphthalic anhydride was isolated and identified. This may also be explained by the preferential formation of *p*-quinones which is possible only with the side ring. It may be pointed out that the simultaneous oxidation of the two side rings would yield benzene-tetracarboxylic acid whose presence could not, however, be confirmed. It is, therefore, reasonable to assume that once the oxidation begins in a side ring, it travels to the adjoining rings and ruptures them successively before phthalic anhydride is formed.

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